
Sufism and Sikhism: Converging Paths to the Realization of Divinity

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ABSTRACT

In medieval India bhakti tradition emerged as the neo-perspective religious perspective mainly to come over the dogmatism of Hindu Brahminical caste system. It was influenced by many external factors. In medieval period Sufism also gained popularity against the Islamic ritualistic orthodoxy. Medieval India had tasted a flavor of both the tradition of religion – Bhakti and Sufi, given the then historical scenario. The concept of Divinity took a new shape. Many new religious concepts emerged to teach the society the new flavor of religious transcendence from ritualistic and rule based orthodox path to the easy way. Guru Nanak was said to be influenced by both Sufi and Bhakti philosophy and revealed a new religious preaching to the world. The teachings of Guru Nanak are said to be a kind of divine revelation as Islam to the Muhammad. Sikhism is a religious adaptation of both Bhakti and Sufi tradition. In this paper I will try to explain how the Sikh concept of divinity is influenced by Sufi concept of the Divine. In order to do so, I would like to begin with the basic features of Divinity explained in Sufism and then analyze the attributes of the Sikh concept of Rab. In the conclusion of my paper, I would like to compare the two concepts and show how Sufi philosophy had an influence on the Sikh concept of divinity.

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1. Introduction:

In medieval India bhakti tradition emerged as the neo-perspective religious tradition mainly to come over the dogmatism of Hindu Brahminical caste system. It was influenced by many external factors. In medieval period Sufism also gained popularity against the Islamic ritualistic orthodoxy. Medieval India had tasted a new flavor of worshipping from both the tradition of religion – Bhakti for Hinduism and Sufi for Islam. The concept of Divinity took a new shape. The Almighty became merciful and graceful personal beloved God rather than mere awful glorious superpower. Many new religious concepts emerged to teach the society the new flavor of religious transcendence from ritualistic and rule based orthodox path to the easy way.

In this paper, how the Sikh concept of divinity is influenced by Sufi concept of the Divine will be discussed. In order to do so, I would like to begin with the basic features of Divinity explained in Sufism and then analyze the attributes of the Sikh concept of *Rab*. In the conclusion of my paper, I would like to compare the two concepts and show how Sufi philosophy had an influence on the Sikh concept of divinity. Both primary and secondary literature review and literary analysis method is used to write this paper.

2. Literature Review:

Primary literatures like Japji and Quran Sharif had been studied and analyzed in order to grasp the nature of the Divine following both religious traditions. As literature analysis is the only method that could have been applied in the said concept, I have studied scholarly writings like A. J. Arberry and A. M. Schimmel for Sufism and writings of Dr. Sher Singh and Dr. Ishar Singh and many research articles for the secondary literature analysis.

3. Research Question:

The research question or the research hypothesis is that the concept of divinity in Sikhism is influenced by the Sufi concept of divinity or not. This article would rather be a comparative analysis of the concept of Divinity in both Sufism and in Sikhism. The Islamic era of medieval India had undergone through a holistic transformation in every aspect of its social life. This includes the cultural and religious modification generated by the interchange of ideologies, beliefs and social practices which results in the modification of the belief system related with religious faith too. The objective of this paper is to identify how much influence does the Sufi concept of Divinity has over the Sikh concept of Divinity.

4. Methodology Used:

I have used descriptive and analytic method of research. I had adopted mainly the literature review (both primary and secondary literatures and articles) method for data collection as the observational or experimental method cannot be applied in this context. After that I had partake the analytic and descriptive method to analyse and compare the concept of the Divine following both Sufism and Sikhism in a comparative way.

5. Concept of the Divine:

Different religions have different ideologies regarding the concept of the Almighty or the Divine Absolute and the relation of the Divinity with humanity and also with the universe. Some religions regard the divinity as the material cause of the world; some religion regard the Divine as both the material and the instrumental cause of the world and some religion regarded the Divine as only the instrumental cause of the world. These difference of understanding of the concept of Divine had been used in constructing the metaphysical system of the religion generating the ideologies like pantheism, panentheism etc. Our chief aim is to discuss the concept of divinity as per Sufism and Sikhism and not other religious system. So, at first we will discuss the Sufi concept of Divinity and then the Sikh concept of Divinity which will be followed by analytical comparison between the two systems.

5.1.Sufism and the Concept of Divinity:

Sufism is considered as Islamic mysticism. Mysticism is a revelation of the Divine Entity without following a particular ritualistic path of any orthodox ritualistic tradition. Religious mysticism has been developed by following the feeling of the essence of the divine entity, not by the faculty of intellect. "Surrender to God" is the meaning of the word Islām itself. Some academics contend that Islamic monotheism has no mystical or imaginative foundation and was revealed to the Prophet by God.

According to Sufism, God or the Divine being is One Supreme Reality. So, the Sufi Saints like Hallaj said that '*Ahn al Haq*' or 'I am the Reality'. called Sufi saints have different perspective regarding the nature of God or the Divinity. According to one tradition God is both immanent and transcendent of this world. On the other hand, according to Rumi, Gazali God is neither immanent nor transcendent, rather he cannot be described as having any of these qualities. He is beyond the grasp of any description. All Sufi saints agree on the point that the attributes of God are infinite because an Infinite Being cannot have finite number of attributes. Sufism also says that the names of the Divinity are eternal infinite and

innumerable as is His attributes. According to Zili (the famous Sufi saint) the names of the Divinity are not separate from the Divine Himself. So, if we remember the name of the Almighty then we are remembering Him. According to Zili the most appropriate name of the Almighty is Allah which reflects all the attributes of the Divine. According to Ibn-al-Arbi, God has three main names- Allah, Al Rahman and Al Rab.

Sufism advocates that Allah is the Creator of this Universe. Sufism also advocates remembrance and singing in praise of the Almighty. Sufi saints have taught that Allah is the beloved and the most kind and merciful being who loves His creation. Sufism as it follows the Islamic tradition has also advocated the service to the mankind.

5.2.Sikhism and Sikh Concept of Divinity:

Guru Nanak, the founder of Sikh tradition, was said to be influenced by both Sufi and Bhakti philosophy and revealed a new religious preaching to the world. Sikhism is a religious adaptation of both Hindu Bhakti and Islamic Sufi tradition. In Puranic Hinduism which is the basis of Hindu Bhakti tradition, Idol worship was the key attribute and Sakara God replaced the ideology of Advaita Nirakara Brahman. On the other hand, ritualistic rigidity of the orthodox Islam also created a distance between the all-merciful Lord with His people. Bhakti and Sufi tradition revived the true essential nature of the Almighty as being Loving and Merciful Creator. Guru Nanak was influenced mostly by the Sufi teaching of monotheism and Hindu Vedic concept of Akshara Brahman. In Japji Mool Mantar the nature of the Divinity has been described by Guru Nanak as-

“Ik Omkar, Sat Naam, Karta Purakh, Nirbhau Nirvair, Akal- Murat, Ayuni Saibhang, Gurprasad.”

The Divine being is One. He is Eternal – all pervading, the Truth, the true Name, Creator, the Supreme Lord of all, Fearless, without any kind of Animosity, Devoid of Birth and Death, Manifested by Himself and can be known only through the Grace of Guru which is described with the terminology *Gurprasad* in the *Mool Mantar* of Jaapji. This concept of monotheistic Divinity in Sikhism is said to be influenced by the Vedic tradition of Brahman. Prof. H. H. Chakladar and Prof. Sunil Kumar Das has propagated this view. But according to some scholars Sikhism and Sikh concept of the Divine is influenced by the Sufi concept of Divine. If we look at the socio-religious perspective of that time we can see the possibility of the later perspective is more rational and logical.

According to Sikh belief, the world is created by divine order or *Hukam*. The world is not created from ex-nihilo but is the manifestation of God. Creation of the world is a continuous process as per Sikh belief. Creation has a particular purpose but man cannot know the purpose of the creation as it is beyond their understanding. Man is considered to be the greatest creation by God. In a human being, life and consciousness can be found to be in the most developed form. In order to achieve salvation, one has to forget his ego completely and become *Gurumukha* or being inclined towards Guru or the religious master instead of *Manamukha* or being self-centred. The ultimate destiny of a man is to be free from the chain of rebirth and be united with the Almighty.

In Sikhism, God is conceived as a single, formless, all-pervading reality called '*Wahe Guru*' and sometimes '*Rab*'. According to Guru Nanak, the Almighty has infinite names. The God is both immanent and transcendent to the world. The God has no caste creed or gender or particular shape. He is eternal and the creator of the Universe. According to Sikhism, God can be experienced through devotion and meditation with complete self-surrender and through following the devotional path of the Gurus and Guru Granth Sahib. Sikhism does not advocate complete asceticism. It rather teaches to love the humankind as they are the creation of the God. If someone truly loves the God, he/she will also love the creatures he has created. That is why Sikhism advocates the idea of the service to the society in the form of *langar* etc.

Sikhism does not believe in the idol worship as according to them God is formless. The all-pervasive eternal nature of God cannot be grasped in any material form or idol. So Sikhism describes God as formless. Another distinctive feature of Sikhism from Hindu Bhakti tradition is that Sikhism does not believe in the Incarnation of the God. Guru Nanak has referred to Rama or Krishna many times in his teaching but they are the names of the God. Rama and Krishna referred by Guru Nanak is not the incarnations of Vishnu but they are the two names of the infinite names of the Almighty. The Divine being eternal cannot take birth because in order to take birth or incarnations the Divine had to limit Himself. So, the Almighty has been described as *Ayuni* or birthless.

6. Comparison of the Concept of Divinity in Sufism and Sikhism:

If we compare the two religious systems discussed above, we can find out many points of similarities in describing the nature of Divinity. First of all, both Sufism and Sikhism advocates the idea of the Divinity as formless and shapeless. According to Sufism and Sikhism the Almighty is eternal and all-pervasive and this nature of the Almighty cannot be accomplished in any materialistic form or worldly

shape. Sikhism is based on the teachings of Guru Nanak who has the Divine Revelation of the Eternal truth. Sufism is the Islamic mysticism and Islam is based on the teachings of Hazrat Muhammed who also had the Divine Revelation of the eternal truth. There is a similarity in Sikh concept of Divinity and Islamic Concept of Divinity in the way of revealing Himself to the mankind.

Secondly, The Sufis propagates the idea of Zikr or remembrance as the means of daily worshipping the Allah or the Almighty. Sufi Sama singing in the praise of Almighty is considered a pious action of meditation. In Sikhism we can also find the act of remembrance (Simran) and singing the song praising the Almighty (Kirtan).

Thirdly, both the religious system teaches the path of Bhakti or Devotional love for the Almighty and is different from Bhakti tradition in the respect of non-idol worship. Fourthly, both religious traditions have accepted the fact that the Almighty has infinite names and attributes. Sikhism and Sufism rejects the idea of God-incarnations and holds that Almighty has many names. The name 'Rab' as the name of the Divinity has accepted by both the traditions.

Conclusion:

The Sikh Concept of divinity has been influenced in many ways by the Islamic mysticism and Sufi metaphysics. As we can see from the above comparison of Sikhism and Sufism, we can clearly see the similarities between the two ideologies. Many scholars have argued that Sikh concept of Formless Singular God is influenced by the Upanishadic concept of the Divinity. Although the Upanishadic concept of Supreme Divinity as Omkar or Akshara Brhaman has been adopted in the Sikh concept of Divinity, clear influences of Sufism in the metaphysical concept of the Supreme Reality can also be seen. The servitude to the mankind and charitable action towards the society is another attribute which is a distinguishing feature of Sikhism is also influenced by the Islamic concept of servitude or Zakat. The conclusion is that Sikh concept of Divinity is an amalgamation of both Hindu Bhakti and Islamic Sufi tradition.

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